

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 79

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 79

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 79:0 A Psalm of Asaph.</p>	<p>Psa. 79:1 מִזְמוֹר לְאַסָּף</p>
<p>Psa. 79:1 O God, the ^anations have ¹invaded ^bYour inheritance; They have defiled Your ^choly temple; They have ^dlaid Jerusalem in ruins. ² They have given the ^e“dead bodies of Your servants for food to the birds of the heavens, The flesh of Your godly ones to the beasts of the earth. ³ They have poured out their blood like water round about Jerusalem; And there was ^a“no one to bury them. ⁴ We have become a ^a“reproach to our neighbors, A scoffing and derision to those around us. ⁵ ^a“How long, O LORD? Will You be angry forever? Will Your ^bjealousy ^c“burn like fire? ⁶ ^a“Pour out Your wrath upon the nations which ^bdo not know You, And upon the kingdoms which ^cdo not call upon Your name. ⁷ For they have ^a“devoured Jacob And ^blaid waste his ¹habitation.</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים בָּאוּ גוֹיִם בְּנִתְּלֹתְךָ טִמְאוּ אֶת־הַיְכָל קִדְשְׁךָ שְׁמוֹ אֶת־יְרוּשָׁלַם לְעַיִים : ² נִתְּנוּ אֶת־נַבְלֹת עֲבָדֶיךָ מֵאֲכָל לְעוֹף הַשָּׁמַיִם בְּשֵׁר חַסִּידֶיךָ לְחִיתוֹ־אָרֶץ : ³ שָׁפְכוּ דַמָּם כַּמַּיִם סְבִיבוֹת יְרוּשָׁלַם וְאֵין קוֹבֵר : ⁴ הֵינּוּ חֲרָפָה לְשִׁכְנֵינוּ לְעַג וְקָלָם לְסַבִּיבוֹתֵינוּ : ⁵ עַד־מָה יְהוָה תִּפְאַנֵּךְ לְנֹצֵחַ תִּבְעַר כְּמוֹ־אֵשׁ קִנְאֶתְךָ : ⁶ שִׁפְךָ חַמָּתְךָ אֶל־הַגּוֹיִם אֲשֶׁר לֹא־ יָדְעוּךָ וְעַל מַמְלָכוֹת אֲשֶׁר בְּשִׁמְךָ לֹא קָרְאוּ : ⁷ כִּי אָכַל אֶת־יַעֲקֹב וְאֶת־נְוֹהוּ הַשָּׁמוּ : אֶל־תִּזְכֹּר לָנוּ עֲוֹנוֹת רַאשֵׁינִים מִיָּהָר יִקְדְּמוּנוּ רַחֲמֶיךָ כִּי דִלְוֵנוּ מְאֹד : ⁹</p>
<p>Psa. 79:8 ^a“Do not remember ¹the iniquities of <i>our</i> forefathers against us; Let Your compassion come quickly to ^bmeet us, For we are ^cbrought very low.</p>	

⁹ ^aHelp us, O God of our salvation,
for the glory of ^bYour name;

And deliver us and ^{1c}forgive our
sins ^dfor Your name's sake.

¹⁰ ^aWhy should the nations say,
"Where is their God?"

Let there be known among the
nations in our sight,

^bVengeance for the blood of Your
servants which has been shed.

¹¹ Let ^athe groaning of the prisoner
come before You;

According to the greatness of
Your ¹power preserve ²those who are
^adoomed to die.

¹² And return to our neighbors
^asevenfold ^binto their bosom

¹The ^creproach with which they
have reproached You, O Lord.

¹³ So we Your people and the ^asheep
of Your ¹pasture

Will ^bgive thanks to You forever;

To all generations we will ^ctell of
Your praise.

עֲזָרֵנוּ אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׁעֵנוּ עַל-
דְּבַר כְּבוֹד-שְׁמֶךָ וְהַצִּילֵנוּ
וּכְפָר עַל-חַטֹּאתֵינוּ לְמַעַן
שְׁמֶךָ : ¹⁰ לָמָּה אֵי אֱמָרוּ
הַגּוֹיִם אֵי־הֵי־תֵהֶם יוֹדֵעַ
בַּגּוֹיִם [ב] [גוֹיִם] לְעֵינֵינוּ
נִקְלָמַת דָּם-עַבְדֶּיךָ הַשָּׁפוּךְ :
¹¹ הַבּוֹא לְפָנֶיךָ אֲנַקֶּת אֲסִיר
כַּגְּדֹל זְרוּעֶךָ הוֹתֵר בְּנֵי
תְמוֹתָהּ : ¹² וְהָשִׁב לְשִׁכְנֵינוּ
שִׁבְעָתַיִם אֶל-חֵיקָם חֲרָפְתָם
אֲשֶׁר חֲרָפוּךָ אֲדַנִּי : ¹³
וְאִנְחָנוּ עִמָּךָ אִוְצֵאן
מִרְעִיתֶךָ נִוְדָה לָּךְ לְעוֹלָם
לְדָר וָדָר נִסְפָּר תְּהַלְתֶּךָ :

References

Psalm 79:1

¹Lit *come into*

^aLam 1:10

^bPs 74:2

Ps 74:3, 7

^d2 Kin 25:9, 10; 2 Chr 36:17-19; Jer 26:18; 52:12-14; Mic 3:12

Psalm 79:2

^aDeut 28:26; Jer 7:33; 16:4; 19:7; 34:20

Psalm 79:3

^aJer 14:16; 16:4

Psalm 79:4

^aPs 44:13; 80:6; Dan 9:16

Psalm 79:5

^aPs 13:1; 74:1, 9, 10; 85:5; 89:46

^bDeut 29:20; Ezek 36:5; 38:19

Ps 89:46; Zeph 3:8

Psalm 79:6

^aPs 69:24; Jer 10:25; Ezek 21:31; Zeph 3:8

^{b1} 1 Thess 4:5; 2 Thess 1:8

Ps 14:4; 53:4

Psalm 79:7

¹Lit *pasture*

^aPs 53:4

^{b2} 2 Chr 36:19; Jer 39:8

Psalm 79:8

¹Or our *former iniquities*

^aPs 106:6; Is 64:9

^bPs 21:3

Deut 28:43; Ps 116:6; 142:6; Is 26:5

Psalm 79:9

¹Lit *cover over, atone for*

^a2 Chr 14:11

^bPs 31:3

^cPs 25:11; 65:3

^dJer 14:7

Psalm 79:10

^aPs 42:10; 115:2

^bPs 94:1, 2

Psalm 79:11

¹Lit *arm*

²Lit *the children of death*

^aPs 102:20

Psalm 79:12

¹Lit *Their*

^aGen 4:15; Lev 26:21, 28; Ps 12:6; 119:164; Prov 6:31; 24:16; Is 30:26

^bPs 35:13; Is 65:6, 7; Jer 32:18; Luke 6:38

^cPs 74:10, 18, 22

Psalm 79:13

¹Or *pasturing*

^aPs 74:1; 95:7; 100:3

^bPs 44:8

^cPs 89:1; Is 43:21

Targum

Psa. 79:1 A psalm composed by Asaph about the destruction of the Temple. He said in the spirit of prophecy: O God, the Gentiles are entering your inheritance; they have defiled your Temple, they have made Jerusalem a desolation. ² They have given the bodies of your servants to the birds of heaven for food, the flesh of your pious ones to the wild beasts. ³ They have poured out their blood like water around Jerusalem, and there is none to bury. ⁴ We have become a disgrace to our neighbors, a subject of scorn and mockery to our surroundings. ⁵ How long, O LORD, will you be fierce – forever? [How long] will your zeal burn like fire? ⁶ Pour out your wrath on the Gentiles who have not known you, and on the kingdoms who have not prayed in your name. ⁷ For they have destroyed the house of Jacob, and made desolate his Sanctuary. ⁸ Do not remember against us trespasses which were from the beginning; in haste, may your favors go before us, for we have become very destitute. ⁹ Help us, O God our redemption, because of your glorious name; and redeem us, and atone for our sins, for the sake of your name. ¹⁰ Why should the Gentiles say, “Where is their God?” Let the punishment for the blood of your servants that has been spilled be revealed in our sight among the Gentiles. ¹¹ Let the groan of the prisoners come before you like the great strength of your arm; release the children who have been handed over to death. ¹² And give back to our neighbors a seven-fold requital for the punishment of their oaths, and the aspersions they cast on you, O LORD. ¹³ But we are your people, and the sheep of your pasture; we will give thanks in your presence forever; for all generations we will recite your praise.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Midrash Shocher Tov explains that Assaf had been distressed when the earth swallowed his father Korach (Numbers 16:31-33). He lost all hope that his father would return. He had a vision that the earth would also swallow the gates of the Temple while the rest of the Sanctuary was destroyed. The vision concluded with these gates being raised to their former glory.

Verse six

The Psalmist asks for the wrath of God to be placed upon the nations who do not believe in the LORD and have not proclaimed His name. The name of the LORD, HaShem or Adonai, is the holiest name in the Universe. It is so sacred that it could not be said outside the Holy of Holies in the Temple in Jerusalem. The only time it was said was at 3:00 PM on Yom Kippur by the High Priest, who offered a sacrifice to the LORD on behalf of the people.

Pour out Your wrath toward the nations that know You not and upon the kingdoms that have not proclaimed your name.

Verse seven

Many times in the Hebrew Scriptures, the nation of Israel is referred to as Jacob when they sinned and Israel when they were righteous.

For he has devoured Jacob, and they have laid waste His habitation.

Verse nine

When Israel was taken into Exile in Babylon many of the people had abandoned the LORD. They could not believe that the LORD would allow the Babylonians to capture them and destroy the Temple. Overtime they came to understand that it was their error that caused the problem. The people returned to the LORD and after 70 years the LORD helped them.

**Help us, I God of our salvation for the sake of the glory of Your Name;
deliver us, spread forgiveness over our errors for Your Name's sake.**

Verse thirteen

The Psalmist says that the people are confident of their future which goes hand in hand with the universal worship of God.

**But we, Your people and he flock of Your Pasture, we shall render You
homage forever; we shall tell Your fame to generation after generation.**

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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